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PUBLIC PARTICIPATION IN IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROGRAM TO ACCELERATE THE COMPLETION OF ILLITERACY (STUDY CASE IN YALENGGA JAYAWIJAYA REGENCY)

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to describe: factors that cause high rates of illiteracy, public participation in implementing literacy programs, obstacles faced and impacts of such programs for the community. This research is a descriptive study using a qualitative approach. Sources of data is consisted by head of PNFI Jayawijaya regency, Chief of Yalengga district, Chairman of the Department PNFI Kemah Injil Church Synode, Chairman of PKBM Yalengga and Tirluk, citizens of illiterate. Analysis data used in this research is qualitative method. The results show that the causative factors in height illiteracy figures in Yalengga District consists of: poverty population, school dropout basic level, drop out PLS program, social conditions, culture and gender equality, teacher absenteeism in schools and the geographical location of schools away from some of the villages/districts. Implementation of the programs required participation from government and society. Government supports on these programs are to build cooperation and partnership, strengthen of human resources and providers, facilitate issuance of SUKMA and perform the functions of control and evaluation. Community participation is directly involved as program providers (Church and PKBM), facilitators directly involved as tutors and directly involved as illiterate learners. Obstacles encountered in the implementation of the program are the level of participation of the community, tutors, learners; agency management, methods and teaching materials, cooperation, partnership and rural development. Literacy programs have a positive impact for the community, they were able to continue their education equally, spiritual impact, economics and for individual with self-esteem and confidence.

Keywords: *Public participation, literacy program, Rural Area Papua*

1. Introduction

Science, skills, and education are the basic elements that determine the dexterity of a person thinking about himself and his environment. A person who is able to change himself to be better will be able to change his family, later can change the region and then able to change the country to a better direction. But the fact, ideal condition is still far from expectations.

Education conditions in Indonesia now days still require various improvements in various fields. There are still backward people and untouched by decent education, many dropout rates and also many people who suffer from illiteracy status. Literacy in Indonesia existed since the colonial era and the beginning of Indonesia independence, and Government

continues to change it, various policies and programs for the elimination of illiteracy in Indonesia through formal, non formal and informal education.

Due to the importance of these illiteracy problems, in international become one of the determinants development level of a nation, which is measured from the level of literacy of its population to determine the Human Development Index (HDI). The results of United Nations Development Program (UNDP) assessment in 2013 Indonesia show an increment from ranked 111 in 2004 and 2009 into rank 108 in 2013, but still below China and Thailand. One Indicator causes of low HDI rating is the high population of illiterate people. The low human development index indicates the low competitiveness of the nation in life.

Table 1.1 Indonesia Rank Based on Human Development Index (HDI) In comparison with some Asian country, Year 2000 – 2013

Country	Years					
	2000	2002	2003	2004	2009	2013
Thailand	76	70	74	76	87	89
Malaysia	61	59	58	59	67	62
Philippina	77	77	85	83	115	117
Indonesia	109	110	112	111	111	108
China	99	96	104	94	92	91
Vietnam	108	109	109	112	116	121

Source: UNDP HDI Rank (2000, 2002, 2003, 2004, 2009&2013)

The data show high rates of illiteracy throughout Papua especially in rural areas especially for young girls. There are 40% of population aged between 15-59 classified as illiterate, high drop-out rates and Children that out-of-school and imbalances gender to get an access for education in all levels of education. The high rates of teachers and headmasters defaulters in districts at mountain areas (up to 48% of teachers and 70% of school principals) (ACDP, 2014) are very serious concerns and tremendous damage to the quality and trust of education services in hinterland of Papua.

Total data of illiteracy in Papua reach 634,243 people in 2012. 2013 Program, Central Government prioritizes to completing illiteracy in 26 districts in Papua Province and Year 2014 prioritizes 60,000 people to complete the program in 15 densely populated districts, namely Jayawijaya regency, Lani Jaya, Yahukimo, Puncak, Tolikara, Paniai, Puncak Jaya, Nduga, Pegunungan Bintang, Deiyai, Yalimo, Asmat, Dogiyai, Intan Jaya and Mamberamo Tengah.

In 2014 Jayawijaya Regency comes as the first of 15 districts that an illiteracy rate in Papua Province must be completed with total number of people illiteracy reach 65,965 people. The total target has to be completed in 2014 is 9,200 people. Yalengga District is one of the districts in Jayawijaya regency that participate in the program. The illiteracy completion program has been implemented by several institutions in the Yalengga district since 2000. But until today there are many people found with illiteracy status despite various literacy education services has been widely held using various methods, strategies in learning. People in Yalengga District have not been able to develop the potential and improve their life to be better.

There are some people cannot read, counting and speaking Indonesian correctly.

Davis (1962) said "Participation is defined as the mental and emotional involvement of a person in a group situation which encourages him to contribute to group goals and share responsibility in them." Community development always seeks to maximize participation that aims to get everyone in Communities are actively involved in community processes and activities to recreate the future of society and individuals. Thus participation is an important part of empowerment and growth of consciousness. The more active participants, the more complete their participation, the more ideal the sense of ownership and community processes will be realized (Jim & Frank, 2008).

Based on participatory systems and mechanisms, Cohen and Uphoff (1977) in Kannan, (2002) differentiate participation into four types: a) participation in decision making, b) participation in implementation, c) participation in benefit, and participation in evaluation. Participation in decision making is community participation in decision-making processes and organizational policies. Participation in this type is giving the opportunity to the public in expressing their opinion to assess a plan or program to be determined. The community is also giving an opportunity to assess a decision or policy in progress.

Literacy (Literacy) is simply defined as the ability to read, write and count. For illiterate adults, literacy skills are not only able to read, write and count, but rather emphasize function in everyday life (Archer, 1996). Widely, Literacy is defined as the basic knowledge and skills required by all citizens and become one of the foundations for the mastery of other life skills.

Literacy education is a type of non formal education service for people who have not and want to have the ability to read, write and count (calistung), which is functional for their life. People learning not only have calistung abilities, communicate in Indonesian language and business or livelihood skills, but can also adapt and survive in an ever-changing life. Literacy education program is oriented to everyday life by exploiting the potential that exists in surrounding environment, so that citizens learn and society can improve the quality and standard of living. Priority of basic literacy education is between ages 15-49 years old with status of tuna akara and has commitment to follow the activity.

The purpose of this research is to know the factors causing high number of illiteracy, to get information about type of public participation in implementation of the illiteracy completion program, to know the constraints faced by the organizers in the implementation of the program and to get information on the impact of the program in completing the tuna Script for community life in Yalengga District of Jayawijaya Regency.

2. Method

This research was conducted in Yalengga District, Jayawijaya Regency for six months, from December 2014 until May 2015. The type of research used in this study is descriptive qualitative. Researchers are one of important element in qualitative research or called as key instrument. Sources of data used in this research are PNFI field of Jayawijaya Regency, Head of Yalengga District, Head of Department of PNFI Synod of Gereja Kemah Injil in Tanah Papua, Chairman PKBM Yalengga, Chairman of PKBM Tirluk, Tutor and Residents Learning illiteracy. Data collection methods used was in-depth interviews, observation and documentation. Data analysis techniques used are data reduction, data presentation, conclusion and verification (Miles & Huberman, 1994). Validity testing of data was done by using reference, peer examination / supervisor and Discussion Group (FGD).

3. Results

a. Factors that cause high levels of illiteracy

The findings of factors causing high rates of illiteracy are: a) never schooling, b) family factors not giving support and motivation for children to remain in school, c) drop out, d) teacher absenteeism in school, e) Geographical, f) Not supportive environmental factors, g) cultural factors that people still hold and live in, and h) economic factors that society is generally

below the poverty line and making basic needs a priority for their lives.

b. Forms of community participation on implementation of illiteracy completion program

Forms of community participation in the implementation of basic literacy programs are: (a) Community institutions (Church, PKBM, Yayasan) are directly involved as program organizers. (B) The pastor voluntarily assumes the responsibility of being a tutor / facilitator of basic literacy programs; and (c) citizens as illiterate status reporters, directly involved as basic literacy learners.

c. Constraints faced by program organizers in implementing illiteracy programs.

The implementation of the illiteracy program in Yalengga district, there are many obstacles faced by various parties. Some obstacles faced by the local government as an extension of the central government, the organizers, tutors and residents learn illiteracy: (a) Low understanding of the importance of education, especially basic literacy education, (b) in general community needs is to fulfill of basic needs, therefore learning/education is not their priority (c) both tutor and people not active in learning (d) lack of training funding, evaluation and monitoring, (e) lack of coordination of work among local governments and program providers, (f) geographical factors for monitoring functions, (g) lack of learning guidance book/teaching manual, (h) no electricity / lighting to study at night, (i) and lack of self learning reference.

d. The impact of illiteracy programs on community life in Yalengga District

Findings impact of basic literacy education programs for local communities are: (a) continuing education of equality, (b) independence to learn and develop, (c) potential development, and (d) to raise self-esteem and self-confidence from the citizens learning itself

4. Discussion

a. Factors contributing to the high rate of illiteracy

From the findings factors causing the high lift of illiteracy in Yalengga District, the following is a further discussion.

1) Cultural factors include: customary festivals, which in those events disturb the lesson schedule of illiteracy and education in general; Pig farming and marriage systems,

- where parents find it difficult to sell pigs for educational purposes; And the role of men and women, in which the residents learn illiteracy is more dominant on women. The role of Dani female influences the participation of women in education and illiteracy learning.
- 2) Economic factors: Yalengga community routines and priorities exist in the fulfillment of basic needs.
 - 3) Political factors: Population data are quite diverse from several sources. Population data is data for political needs, thus impacting on the increase of illiteracy rate.
 - 4) Social factors of social consideration: encompassing geographic conditions for less strategic locations of schools, poor parental understanding of education.
 - 5) Learning conditions: covering limited learning facilities and infrastructure; Teaching materials and reading materials was lack, administrative tools and financial were not functioned maximum; The limitations of tutors that coming from different educational backgrounds, there are 17 letters are rarely or not used in the local language, making it difficult on the learning process; As well as a lack of understanding on graduation standards of learning citizens.
 - 6) Factors of teacher absenteeism: where teachers are not on duty for long periods of time, thus children does not get their right to learn.
- 3) Strengthening the organizing agency: by issuing a decision letter for 40 PKBMs, another 24 were in process. Provide operational assistance, organizer fee, and equality education teaching materials, laptop, printer and physical building that has been realized with 4 PKBM buildings that have been built.
 - 4) Facilitate the issuance of SUKMA.
 - 5) Perform monitoring and evaluation functions: although there is still limited application of monitoring and evaluation function in field.

The type of participation in the implementation of illiteracy impairment program is participation in implementation (Cohen and Uphoff, 1977) which means participation or participation of the community in illiteracy completion activities based on established programs.

Types of community involvement in the program are:

- 1) The Church Institution: to be involved as an organizer with the responsibility to exercise spiritual literacy for Church Congregation with illiterate status; Fundraising for tutor training funds; Procurement, printing and distribution of teaching manuals; As well as Church building donations used as learning venue.
- 2) PKBM Institution: involved as an organizer; Tutors who come from the Church, are committed to teaching; Citizens learn to be directly involved as illiterate citizens to support the program.

Community participation in the implementation of the acceleration program for illiteracy is urgently needed, but there are several factors that sometimes hamper the participation of the community itself, among others: the level of education; The step of feeling 'trust' or 'confidence'; Society has not experience yet or uplifted its interests; As well as the program's goals and benefits are not clear enough for public.

The Church is an organization that exists in every region inland of Papua. If in a district does not have a school, it is certain that the church exists and provides services to the community. Inland of Papua, the church not only provides spiritual services, but provides health care, agriculture, livestock and education. In the case of PKBM in Yalengga District, Church in cooperation with the community to provide a package of learning services in the form of a

- b. Community participation model on implementation of acceleration program for illiteracy in Yalengga District

The form of support from the Regional Government through the Office of Education and Culture of Non-Formal Education in the implementation of literacy education in Jayawijaya Regency, especially in Yalengga district is by:

- 1) Establish cooperation and partnership with the organizing institutions such as the Church, PKBM, NGO / Foundation and also universities in the region to implement the illiteracy programs.
- 2) Strengthening human resources: by providing training / comparative studies for PKBM leaders at home and abroad.

Teaching and Learning Center. The entry of Christianity in Papua in 1855 marked the beginning of modern education in untouched area (Modouw, 2013).

Based on the above obstacle factors, the following is a solution or strategy taken to foster community participation according to Jim and Frank (2008): bottom up approaching; Focusing on the process rather than on results; Raising public awareness of the purpose and benefits of activities; Collaborate and coordinate effectively; And oriented to build society.

c. Obstacle faced in organizers of illiteracy programs

From the results of interviews with informants and observations conducted at the program organizers, the obstacles that become interference are: public participation in general; Tutor participation; Participation of illiterate citizens; Institutional management; Methods and teaching materials; cooperation; And village development where Yalengga district has no electricity yet.

From some of the above obstacles, the program of acceleration of illiteracy completion is still carried out. Strategies taken are: change the approaching from the bottom; Institutions are always oriented on process rather than outcomes; Giving motivation for learning or inactive tutors; Cooperation between Dinas and teachers who manage their promotion by involving them in completing illiteracy; As well as institutional orientation to build communities with transparent funds usage.

d. The analysis impact from illiteracy completion program for community life in the Yalengga District

Literacy is a right for everyone. This concept is related to the principle of benefit, namely literacy education provides benefits to individuals, families, communities and nations. The results of impact interviews of illiteracy completion program for the Yalengga district community are: a) Education: illiterate people can continue their education by learning. B) Spiritual: the Church's seriousness in carrying out illiteracy programs has an impact for the congregation to be able to read and study the Bible itself. C) Economics: literate learners can improve their knowledge, business and income. D) Social: people's self-esteem and their confidence are lifted through literacy education.

With the program of accelerated completion of illiteracy for the illiterate people, indirectly the government and the organizers

empower the community or learners how to grow. Efforts to empower the community or learners can be seen from three sides namely, first: create an atmosphere / climate that allow potential learners Develop (enabling). Empowerment is an effort to build, encourage and motivate and raise awareness of their potential as well as to develop it. Second, strengthen the potential or power owned by student (empowering). Third, increase the participation of student in the decision-making process that concerns himself and society.

Functional of Literacy can be interpreted as ability to read and write. According to Arief and Napitupulu (1997), literacy is defined as the basic knowledge and skills that required by universe in a rapidly changing, as a human right. Meanwhile, according to Kusnadiet al. (2003: 53), functional literacy is one type of Non formal School Education services for people who have not and want to have the ability to read, write and count and then use it and meaningful for his life. They not only have the ability to read, write and count as well as having skills to do business or livelihood skills only, but also can survive in life.

Literacy is a catalyst for participating in social, cultural, political, economic and community empowerment, and as a part for lifelong learning. Functional literacy emphasizes an ability to handle a new condition that created by the community environment, thus learners have the functional ability that is functioning for self and community. The purpose of functional literacy is how to pursue the ability, understanding and adjustment to adjust the conditions of life and their working activity. More broadly, literacy seeks to build society, through the change of individuals level and society, with this equity, opportunity and global understanding. With the existence of PKBM in the Yalengga District, the community is able to pursue the opportunity to improve in the education field which leads to increase their self-confident and self-esteem.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion that have been analyzed, below are the conclusions from this research:

- a. The factors causing high illiteracy rates in Yalengga district of Jayawijaya Regency are: population poverty, dropout rate, drop out of PLS program, social condition, cultural factor, political factor and gender equality, teacher absence in school for some time and the geographical location of

- schools is far enough for some villages or districts.
- b. To overcome the high rate of illiteracy, a program to accelerate the completion of illiteracy by optimizing the function of planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation.
 - c. In the implementation of the program requires participation and cooperation from government and community to ensure the success of illiteracy completion program. The government participation through the education office of Jayawijaya Regency by build the cooperation and partnership, strengthening human resources, strengthening program organizers, facilitating the issuance of SUKMA and perform monitoring and evaluation function. Type of community participation is become as program organizer institution that is realized with a sense of responsibility to discourage illiterate congregation residents thus people able to read and understand the contents of the Bible as well as other reading material. It's the same with the tutor teachers involved in it. While the learners of illiteracy are directly involved to learn and to complete their duties and responsibilities in the Church and society.
 - d. In the implementation of many obstacles faced by the organizers, is: community participation, tutor participation, participation of learning citizens, management institutions, methods and teaching materials, cooperation and partners as well as development of the village. Strategies taken by program organizers to handle the above obstacles with approaching 'bottom-up', orientation on the process rather than results/outcome, raising community awareness, cooperation and partnership and orientation to build a community with transparent processing of funds.
 - e. Thus this basic literacy program has a positive impact on people in Yalengga district to continue to equality of education, the spiritual impact that the congregation able to read the Bible and increase their faith and devotion to a supreme God, the economic impact for increasing people's incomes and Give impact to individuals to improve their self-esteem and self-confidence

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